

Instructions for Authors

Purpose and Scope

The *Cambodian Journal of Natural History* (ISSN 2226–969X) is an open access, peer-review journal published biannually by the Centre for Biodiversity Conservation at the Royal University of Phnom Penh. The Centre for Biodiversity Conservation is a non-profit making unit, dedicated to training Cambodian biologists and the study and conservation of Cambodia's biodiversity.

The *Cambodian Journal of Natural History* publishes original work by:

- Cambodian or foreign scientists on any aspect of Cambodian natural history, including fauna, flora, habitats, management policy and use of natural resources.
- Cambodian scientists on studies of natural history in any part of the world.

The journal especially welcomes material that enhances understanding of conservation needs and has the potential to improve conservation management in Cambodia. The primary language of the journal is English. For full papers, however, authors are encouraged to provide a Khmer translation of their abstract.

Readership

The journal's readers include conservation professionals, academics, government departments, non-governmental organisations, students and interested members of the public, both in Cambodia and overseas. The journal is freely available online from << <https://rupp.edu.kh/cjnh/index.php> >>.

Manuscripts Accepted

The following types of manuscripts are accepted:

- Full papers (2,000–7,000 words, excluding references)
- Short communications (300–2,000 words, excluding references)
- News (<300 words)

Full Papers and Short Communications

Full Papers (2,000–7,000 words, excluding references) and Short Communications (300–2,000 words, excluding references) are welcomed on topics relevant to the journal's focus, including:

- Research on the status, ecology or behaviour of wild species.
- Research on the status or ecology of habitats.
- Checklists of species, whether nationally or for a specific area.
- Discoveries of new species records or range extensions.
- Reviews of conservation policy and legislation in Cambodia.
- Conservation management plans for species, habitats or areas.
- The nature and results of conservation initiatives, including case studies.
- Research on the sustainable use of wild species.

News

Concise reports (<300 words) on news of general interest to the study and management of Cambodia's biodiversity. News items may include, for example:

- Announcements of new initiatives; for example, the launch of new projects, conferences or funding opportunities.
- Summaries of important news from an authoritative published source; for example, a new research technique, or a recent development in conservation.

How to Submit a Manuscript

Manuscripts are accepted on a rolling basis each year and should be submitted by email to the editors (<< **Editor.CJNH@gmail.com** >> or << **Editor.CJNH@rupp.edu.kh** >>). In the covering email, the lead (corresponding) author should provide the names and contact details of at least three suitably qualified reviewers (whom the editors may or may not contact at their discretion) and confirm that:

- The submitted manuscript has not been published elsewhere,
- All of the authors have read the submitted manuscript and agreed to its submission, and
- All research was conducted with the necessary approval and permit from the appropriate authorities.

Authors are welcome to contact the editors at any time if questions arise before or after submitting a manuscript.

Preparation of Manuscripts

Authors should consult previous issues of the journal for general style, and early-career authors are encouraged to consider guidance provided by:

Fisher, M. (2012) Editorial – To shed light on dark corners. *Cambodian Journal of Natural History*, **2012**, 1–2.

Daltry, J., Fisher, M. & Furey, N.M. (2012) Editorial – How to write a winning paper. *Cambodian Journal of Natural History*, **2012**, 97–100.

Manuscripts should be in English and use UK English spelling (if in doubt, Microsoft Word and similar software should be set to check spelling and grammar for 'English (UK)' language). Lines should be double-spaced. Submissions can be in 'doc', 'docx' or 'rtf' format, preferably as a single file attached to one covering email.

The order of sections in the manuscript should be: cover page, main text, references, short biography of each author (optional), tables and figures (including photographs). All pages should be numbered consecutively and continuous line numbering should be used.

Cover page: This should contain the institutions and full postal addresses of all authors and the email address of the corresponding author.

Title: A succinct description of the work, in no more than 20 words.

Abstract: (Full papers only). This should describe, in no more than 250 words, the aims, methods, major findings and conclusions. The abstract should be informative and intelligible without reference to the text, and should not contain any references or undefined abbreviations.

Keywords: (Full papers only). Up to eight pertinent words, in alphabetical order.

Main text: (Short communications). This should avoid the use of headed sections or subsections.

Main text: (Full papers). This should comprise the following sections in order: Introduction, Methods, Results, Discussion and Acknowledgements. Subsections may be included in the Methods, Results and Discussion sections if necessary. If included in the Discussion, conclusions and recommendations should comprise a single paragraph.

References: These should be cited in the text in the form of Stuart & Emmett (2006) or (Lay, 2000). For three or more authors, use the first author's surname followed by *et al.*; for example, Rab *et al.* (2006) or (Khou *et al.*, 2005). Multiple references should be in chronological order, for example, Holloway & Browne (2004); Kry & Chea (2004); Phan (2005); Farrow (2006).

The reference list should be presented in alphabetical order. Cambodian, Vietnamese and other authors who typically write their family name first are presented in the form <surname> <initials> without a comma (thus, Sin Sisamouth becomes Sin S.). Western author names are presented in the form <surname> <comma> <initials> (thus Charles Robert Darwin becomes Darwin, C.R.).

The titles of articles and journals should be written in full.

The following are examples of house style:

Papers:

Berzins, B. (1973) Some rotifers from Cambodia. *Hydrobiologia*, **41**, 453–459.

Neang T. (2009) Liquid resin tapping by local people in Phnom Samkos Wildlife Sanctuary, Cambodia. *Cambodian Journal of Natural History*, **2009**, 16–25.

Tanaka S. & Ohtaka A. (2010) Freshwater Cladocera (Crustacea, Branchiopoda) in Lake Tonle Sap and its adjacent waters in Cambodia. *Limnology*, **11**, 171–178.

Books and chapters:

Khou E.H. (2010) *A Field Guide to the Rattans of Cambodia*. WWF Greater Mekong Cambodia Country Programme, Phnom Penh, Cambodia.

MacArthur, R.H. & Wilson, E.O. (1967) *The Theory of Island Biogeography*. Princeton University Press, Princeton, USA.

Rawson, B. (2010) The status of Cambodia's primates. In *Conservation of Primates in Indochina* (eds T. Nadler, B. Rawson & Van N.T.), pp. 17–25. Frankfurt Zoological Society, Frankfurt, Germany, and Conservation International, Hanoi, Vietnam.

Reports:

Lic V., Sun H., Hing C. & Dioli, M. (1995) *A Brief Field Visit to Mondolkiri Province to Collect Data on Kouprey (Bos sauveli), Rare Wildlife and for Field Training*. Unpublished report to Canada Fund and IUCN, Phnom Penh, Cambodia.

Theses:

Yeang D. (2010) *Tenure rights and benefit sharing arrangements for REDD: a case study of two REDD pilot projects in Cambodia*. MSc thesis, Wageningen University, Wageningen, The Netherlands.

Websites:

IUCN (2010) *2010 IUCN Red List of Threatened Species*. [Http://www.redlist.org](http://www.redlist.org) [accessed 1 December 2010].

About the Author(s): This section is optional for Full Papers and Short Communications. It should describe the main research interests of each author (<150 words each), apart from what is obvious from the subject of the manuscript and the authors' affiliations.

Tables and figures (including plates): All tables and figures should be cited in the text and placed at the end of the manuscript. These should be self-explanatory, have an appropriate caption and be placed on separate pages. Figures, including maps, should ideally be in black and white. Plates (photographs) should be included only if they are of good quality and form part of evidence that is integral to the study (e.g. a camera trap photograph of a rare species).

Appendices: Long tables and other supporting materials, such as questionnaires, should be placed in Appendices.

Species names: The first time a species is mentioned, its scientific name should follow without intervening punctuation: e.g., Asian elephant *Elephas maximus*. English names should be in lower case throughout except where they incorporate a proper name (e.g., Asian flycatcher, Swinhoe's minivet, long-billed vulture).

Abbreviations: Full expansion should be given at first mention in the text.

Units of measurement: Use metric units for measurements of area, mass, height, etc.

Review and Editing

All authors are strongly advised to ensure that their spelling and grammar is checked by a native English speaker before the manuscript is submitted to the journal. The editorial team reserves the right to reject manuscripts that need extensive editing for spelling and grammar.

All manuscripts are subject to rigorous peer review by a minimum of two qualified reviewers.

Proofs will be sent to authors as a portable document format (PDF) file attached to an email note. Acrobat Reader can be downloaded free of charge from <www.adobe.com> to view the PDF files. Corrected proofs should be returned to the Editor within three working days of receipt. Minor corrections can be communicated by email.

Authors are permitted to post their papers on their personal and institutional webpages on condition that access is free and no changes are made to the content.

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